

INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL FACTORS AFFECTING THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL OUTLOOK OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN GLOBAL INFORMATION ENVIRONMENT.

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ABSTRACT

In this article, it is necessary that the reforms carried out in our country today form an important image of the education of the younger generation, which is our future. Because it turned out that the result of the reforms carried out in the field of education and education and the attitude to this system in society is not consistent. Some issues on the different effects of problems in the sphere of Education directly on the moral and moral appearance of young people have been discussed.

Also, within the framework of the topic, the manifestations of social factors affecting the spiritual and moral worldview of the youth put forward are reflected.

To date, how rich is the intellectual potential of a person, considering the existence of the power of creativity, the possibilities of many new technological methods of further improvement of mental capabilities are growing.

At present time millions of our young people are living with the spirit of acquiring knowledge, creativity, developing intellectual thinking, adapting their intellectual potential to the modern demand, competing with the youth of the world, we should create more effective solutions to opportunities and educate young specialists mentally and spiritually.

Regarding this, how we can achieve intellectual and creative excellence? How

can we shape our expert staff, like our great ancestors, the development of intelligence?

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Mirziyoyev said in his speech at the Youth Forum of Uzbekistan, which was held on December 25, 2020, " no matter how difficult it may be, we must look for ways that are unique and effective in terms of youth education, in harmony with the present. We must spare our children from the mood of destructive and harmful ideas, crime, drug addiction, apathy, spiritual poverty"1.

In order to reach the level of the developed countries of the world, it will have laid the foundation for progress as long as the nation is deeply aware of what to raise its potential. Because, when people

consciously do not strive for the future, that is, when the ideas of aspiration, new Learning, Mastering, and life application do not take on a mass scale (do not cover the minds of so many), creative thinking, the ideas of independent thinking remain a “dry slogan”. One factor in achieving creative and independent thinking is the social consciousness and the social demands and needs that it creates.

Today, having clear goals and directions can not be imagined without information or mass media. Through the mass media, first of all, people will be aware of the changes taking place in political, social, economic, cultural life as well as in the relations of the world community, the state, it can also perceive, react, accept and become a participant of political processes or, on the contrary, remain objective. But for some reason, we can not imagine our today's way of life without the media. The role and role of mass media in social life is increasing.

In today's globalizing world, it is no secret that information occupies a great place in international and state relations. Therefore, young people in Uzbekistan are also now spreading their own way of thinking and world outlook in the young people who are growing up in our country by means of open information and Information Technologies, various information sources observed in the computer and internet systems. Among the information that is spreading, there are also sources that can serve to improve the quality of specialist personnel training, which are of a positive nature according to their sphere of influence.

However, some information has a negative impact on the minds of young

people, which simply can not be ignored. For example, various dirt, militant films, News that express the views of different streams, internet sites aimed at misrepresenting the events taking place in our country, can be an example of this.

The role of modern information and communication technologies in the educational process in the use of vocational college students during their educational activities in the service of increasing the potential of young people is being carried out in recent years. As a result of this, first of all, the existing educational institutions in our country had the opportunity to use a variety of information resources. As modern computer, information and communication technologies have entered into the educational practice, classes have begun to be organized in completely new forms, methods and methods. In educational institutions, there are opportunities to remotely teach the global and local system, to individualize its stratification. The establishment of education on the basis of information and Communication Technologies is considered as a task to be solved at the level of public policy in our country.

It should be noted that the strategy for the introduction of information and Communication Technologies has been developed in all educational institutions of our country, and it is determined to use modern computer technologies installed in schools and educational institutions not only in the teaching of “information technologies”, but also in the teaching of all subjects, in the organization and management of educational processes

Special attention is paid to the introduction of information and

communication technologies in educational practice at all stages of continuous education in our country. In particular, the introduction of information and communication technologies into the educational process, the creation, development, localization and popularization of multimedia educational programs, the introduction of electronic educational resources into the educational process is an expression of an important pedagogical update. And this requires a quick solution to the problem of computer literacy of each teacher.

As a result of the complete connection of distance education in educational institutions to the "Ziyonet" network, they have a single Information Education Network. In this case, the pedagogical communities will be able to exchange information quickly; the process of popularization of work experiences of advanced teachers, modern educational technologies will be accelerated; real conditions are created for the fast delivery of e-learning tools to educational institutions and, ultimately, for the acquisition of thorough and in-depth knowledge of the pupils on the basis of the requirements

Updates in the pedagogical process take place based on computer and information communication technologies, are subject to implementation in practice. Therefore, the professional need of all teachers to have skills in computer literacy and information and communication technologies as well as become a key element of pedagogical skills.

Methods and forms of using modern Information Communication Technologies in increasing the intellectual potential of

young people create creative conditions for creating new technologies in the process of teaching subjects. After all, it serves to shape the creative worldview, while increasing the intellectual potential of young people.

In place of the conclusion, it should be noted that in the current global information environment, the influence of various foreign ideas on the spiritual and moral outlook of young people is very strong. Because today, when ideological polygons from nuclear polygons are powerful, millions of information flow into our minds whether we want it or not. At the time of their adoption, we have a different system of views and opinions. The fact that they have a creative or destructive character depends on our level of upbringing and our life experience. The internet system is used for various purposes, to get acquainted, to receive information, to exchange information, to learn languages, to transfer time from idleness. This leads to a variety of reception and transmission of information from a variety of objectives. As a result, we can see that students have access to sites, social networks with xar-type unhealthy views without knowing it. The development of information technology requires people to have in-depth knowledge of information and Communication Technology. At the same time, mass media: radio and television do not affect the moral worldview of young people. From the above points of view, all educational institutions, as well as family and Neighborhood Cooperation are being promoted, videoconferences are being organized.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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